

D 3.1 BUILD Value proposition and Engagement Strategy

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BUILD

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1 Introduction

The aim of this report is to provide an engagement strategy based on value propositions created for all actions and deliverables conducted within the BUILD project for Public Innovation Procurers and Innovation Providers. These value propositions have been created in a workshop format with all consortium partners present, using an empathy map and a value proposition canvas. The findings from the empathy map and value proposition canvas provide valuable insights into how to improve the public innovation procurement process, and make sure the audiences are correctly engaged.

The report is divided into two parts. The first part includes all the insights generated from the Empathy Map and Value Proposition Canvas to generate the Value Proposition Statements. The second part dives into relating the value proposition statements to communication activities and provides an engagement strategy.

2 Methodology

To create unique value proposition statements that can be used for reaching out to key target audiences and encapsulating all value generated by the project, it is important that all partners can provide adequate input. Hence, the consortium has hosted a brainstorming workshop on the 3rd of February in which the foundation has been created.

In this workshop, partners went through all the steps of the Empathy Map and Value proposition Canvas for the public innovation procurers which resulted in newly found insights and a deeper understanding of the purpose of BUILD. Each step consisted of a five-minute brainstorm exercise in which everyone was silent except for what they wrote down on a post-it note. This avoided unnecessary discussion and only room for divergent thinking. After the five-minute brainstorming exercise, post-it results were quickly clustered along overarching themes. For public innovation providers there was only limited time – so the first steps of the empathy map have been skipped. All the input generated from the brainstorming exercise has been analysed and will be presented in its raw form as well as in a short summary.

3 Value Propositions

3.1 Procurers Empathy Map

An empathy map is a collaborative tool a team can use to gain a deeper insight into their customers. Much like a user persona, an empathy map can represent a group of users, such as the customer segment. An empathy map helps to map what a design team news about the potential audience. This tool helps to understand the reason behind some actions a user takes deeply. This tool helps build empathy towards users and helps the design team shift focus from the product to the users who are going to use the product.

This forms the basis to match the consortium`s actions and deliverables towards the next step. It helps to answer the question: who are we doing it for? So that we can later answer the question: how are our own actions and deliverables valuable for them? And in what form and channel would they like to be approached?

3.1.1 WHO are we empathising with?

To answer this question, the consortium brainstormed for 5 minutes using the following prompts:

- Who is the person we want to understand?
- What is the situation they are in?
- What is their role in the situation?

This resulted in the following inputs:

- Local
- Changing world
- Open minded willing to learn something new.

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- Busy time schedule
 - Has many different projects at the same time.
 - No time to get into details.
 - Enthusiastic and open but no time to get into something new.
 - Good planner and organiser
 - Used to do things a certain way.
 - Have their own way of facing changes.
 - Need to understand the ins and out of the assignment.
 - They are professionals in procurement processes but probably not specialised to any other specific field.
 - Leading a team of procurers and being responsible for the adoption of the new strategy among target/executioners.
 - Ensure that all stakeholders involved are happy with the new strategy and to act as a convincing leader of the procurers.

Which are summarised in the following description:

A public procurement officer is a local professional who is open minded and willing to learn something new in a changing world. He/she is a busy person and has many different projects on his plate at the same time. He/she doesn't have time to get into details, but he/she is enthusiastic and open to new things. He/she is a good planner and organiser and is used to doing things a certain way. He/she is also able to face changes in his own way and needs to understand the ins and outs of an assignment. He/she is an experienced professional in procurement processes, but he/she is not specialised in any other specific field, including the specific field where the procurement happens.

3.1.2 What do they need to DO?

To answer this question, the consortium brainstormed using the following prompts:

What do they need to do differently?

What job(s) do they want or need to get done?

What decision(s) do they need to make?

How will they know they were successful?

This resulted in the following inputs:

- Procure the right project that won't waste public money.
- They must remain critical.
- They need to lead a procurement project from start to finish.
- Able to justify purchases.
- They need to get all needed stakeholders on board and understand who they are.
- Need to understand why to make changes in the process is sometimes important.
- They must keep both client and market satisfied.
- Build a team to support the process.
- They provide a heads up during the process.
- Measure successfulness afterwards by doing a interview with the project leader
- They need to prioritise the different handlings.
- Prioritise what to do first.
- Take lessons learnt from previous experience.

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- They need to make sure the project follows procurement laws.
 - Need to choose the right method for the procurement.
 - Manage internal knowledge sharing.
 - Stay up to date with common practices.

Which are summarised in the following description:

Public innovation procurers are responsible for ensuring that the right projects are procured, that public money is not wasted, and that stakeholders are onboarded and satisfied. They must remain critical, lead projects from start to finish, justify purchases, prioritise tasks and handlings, take lessons from previous experiences, choose the right method for procurement, manage internal knowledge sharing, stay up to date with common practices, and measure successfulness afterwards.

3.1.3 What do they SEE?

To answer this question, the consortium brainstormed using the following prompts:

What do they see other municipalities do?

What do they see in their immediate environment?

What do they see others saying and doing?

What are they watching and reading?

This resulted in the following inputs:

- Innovation projects that slipped through the net.
- See others joining national buyer groups.
- If they are more involved in a certain kind of topic, they can join events/ information meetings.
- See when following a course, they get to know other buyers from other municipalities and get their contact details.
- See when people are not following the rules.
- They see bad cases or struggles.
- They see overlap.
- They see success cases.
- They see other innovations.
- See that after Covid-19 pandemics many more cases went to court.
- They read national guidelines.
- They read new legislations and guidelines.
- Look for support from Excellence Centres.
- They utilise local competence centres that bring procurers and their best practises together.
- They see Tendered to see how others do it.

Which are summarised in the following description:

Public innovation procurers see a wide variety of cases, from successful innovations to struggles and overlap, as well as changes in legislation and guidelines. They collaborate with others from different municipalities and access resources from excellence centres and local competence centres to ensure the best outcomes for their projects.

3.1.4 What do they SAY?

To answer this question, the consortium brainstormed using the following prompts:

What have we heard them say?

What can we imagine them saying?

This resulted in the following inputs:

- "Now we have to call it innovation, before it was just normal procedures".
- "We need to spend more money".
- Hear them say the working group is personally involved with potential customers.
- "You better get it done in four weeks!"
- "Procurement cannot be done within 4 weeks".
- "Do we have enough information to go through this project?"
- "I am very tired".
- Complaint that PPI is often taking longer time.
- "That seems a bit too risky."
- Explaining and translating procurement law.
- Explaining procurement
- "What is the main target in this project and can we let the bidders offer their own unique solution?"
- "Do we really need to buy that? or can we do it differently?"
- "What could we state as a quality criterion to this procurement project?"
- "Do we have enough information to go through this project?"
- "How is sustainability considered in this project?"

Which are summarised in the following description:

The public innovation procurers often have to explain and translate procurement law and make sure that sustainability is considered that the main target and quality criteria are stated, and that the bidders are allowed to offer their own unique solution. They must find the best way to spend money, make sure that the project is done without delays and often have to brand procedures as innovation. Despite the workload, they must remain focused and engaged, while also recognizing when something might be too risky despite lacking all the information.

3.1.5 What do they DO?

To answer this question, the consortium brainstormed using the following prompts:

What do they do today?

What behaviour have we observed?

What can we imagine them doing?

This resulted in the following inputs:

- They are working on a development project to improve their departments processes.
- They are checking whether teams are following the schedule, and everything is on time.
- Planning every part of their job
- They are sitting (and probably leading) on a meeting.
- Sometimes they don't follow procedures.
- Do overtime.
- Deal with fires.

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- Go and participate in training and network events.
 - Meet outside of the office.
 - Recognise their own procurements in real life.
 - Checking procurement papers of other colleagues.
 - Asking ideas from colleagues how to deal with a problem.
 - Giving and receiving feedback from colleagues.
 - Understand different kinds of belongings.
 - Discussing a lot of issues with the lawyers.
 - Delve into a specific category to learn.
 - They are the link between working groups and potential customers.

Which are summarised in the following description:

Public innovation procurers coordinate the development of new processes, manage timelines, and ensure procedures are followed, attend meetings and training events, deal with unexpected issues, provide feedback, understand the needs of stakeholders, review procurements, offer ideas to problems, and facilitate communication between working groups and potential customers. Some procurers do not follow procurement procedures which is frowned upon. It is a hectic job with overtime, but seeing their innovative procurements in real life when they walk around the city makes it worth doing.

3.1.6 What do they HEAR?

To answer this question, the consortium brainstormed using the following prompts:

What do they hear others say?

What are they hearing from their friends?

What are they hearing from their colleagues?

What are they hearing second-hand?

This resulted in the following inputs:

"Isn't it hard to lead so many projects that are so different from each other? You must know so much from so many fields of study."

- "Can we decide not to continue with the procurement because we would have liked to make a contract with another company?"
- "Thank you for the money!"
- "Innovative startups have a different way of working than government".
- "Last time we did it that way and it worked, why change?"
- Complaints from the team members
- Their Family & friends often say: "Oh can you give us an assignment?"
- "Why did you choose this procedure/method?"
- Sometimes you hear that working groups are happy with your project leading skills.
- "Maybe we should have thought the criteria more carefully".
- "This could have been done more effectively".
- "Why procurement?!"

Which are summarised in the following description:

Public innovation procurers often hear a variety of comments and questions from stakeholders, ranging from appreciation for their work ("Thank you for the money!") to criticism of their methods

("Maybe we should have thought the criteria more carefully"). They are often asked about the intricacies of their processes ("Can we decide not to continue with the procurement?") and the challenges of leading multiple projects from different fields of study ("Isn't it hard to lead so many projects that are so different to each other?"). They are also asked for favours from family and friends ("Oh can you give us an assignment?") and have to deal with complaints from team members. Nevertheless, they often hear positive feedback as well, such as appreciation for their project leading skills or compliments on their innovative approach.

3.1.7 Summary

Performing the empathy map has proven to be very effective and valuable, especially because we had real public innovation procurers in the room. At first the results might seem very basic and standard, especially for those familiar with the role. However, as we started to fill in more of the prompts, a larger picture started to emerge that was beneficial for people to understand as they gained more empathy for each other and learned to see their position in a different light. The results will be used as a basis for the value proposition canvas, and a summary is provided below:

Public innovation procurers are responsible for ensuring that the right projects are procured, that public money is not wasted and that stakeholders are onboarded and satisfied. They must remain critical, lead projects from start to finish, and justify purchases. They collaborate with others from different municipalities and access resources from excellence centres and local competence centres and explain and translate procurement law and ensure sustainability. They coordinate the development of new processes, manage timelines, and ensure procedures are followed, attend meetings and training events, deal with unexpected issues, and provide feedback. They often hear a variety of comments and questions from stakeholders, ranging from appreciation to criticism. They are also asked for favours and have to deal with complaints, but also receive positive feedback.

3.2 Procurers Value proposition Canvas

The value proposition canvas is a framework which can help ensure that a product or service is positioned around what the customer values and needs. The value proposition canvas focuses on understanding the customers problems and producing products or services that solve them. Because telling people you have a great product does not make them want it. This chapter treats the innovation procurer as the customer and elaborates on the brainstorming outputs leading to the value proposition statement.

3.2.1 Tasks

The consortium used inputs from the Empathy Map and held a short brainstorm exercise. The new results were as follows:

- Schedule monthly/ quarterly team meetings.
- Ensure all meetings are completed within the timeline.
- Monitor and evaluate internal performance KPIs.
- Compose procurement description/ invitation for bidders.
- Identify, assess, and act on risks and unforeseen situations.
- Research and analyse current market conditions and report findings to the contract manager from the municipality.
- Contact other procurers for potential collaboration.

3.2.2 Pains

Pains in the value proposition canvas refers to the challenges, problems, and dissatisfactions that a business's customers are currently facing. Pains can include problems with price, availability, quality, and service. Understanding customer pains can help businesses to identify opportunities for

improvement and create value for customers. Brainstorming about potential pains from the tasks public procurers perform resulted in the following:

- Failure of the procurement project.
- Lack of interest from markets side and no bids.
- If the bidders make complaints.
- Unclear definition of innovation.
- Very specific cases requiring technical knowledge.
- Not enough time to do the process well, step by step (maybe with a market consultation).
- Held back by regulation.
- Working group does not really know what they want to buy.
- Unclear top-level strategy (national/EU level)).
- Lack of budget.
- Emails that are waiting for responses.
- Not enough hands to do the job.
- Time consuming.
- Communication within the working group is not very easy, because they think very much in the grey area (and less practical).
- Lack of engagement in the team.
- Intermunicipal communication problems.

3.2.3 Gains

Gains in the value proposition canvas refer to the benefits, and satisfactions in their job and tasks. It explores what situations and aspects make them happy when they perform their daily duties. Understanding customer gains can help businesses to identify opportunities for exploiting and create value for customers. Brainstorming about potential gains from the tasks public procurers perform resulted in the following:

- Knowledge in expected places.
- Interesting projects with teams of varied skills and knowledge.
- Good practices in place.
- Positive feedback and results.
- Resources and targets met.
- Results achieved.
- Procurement in mature markets.
- Good suppliers.
- Engaged bidders.
- Understanding and support from supervisors.
- Ability to discuss with colleagues.
- Problems heard and solutions considered.

3.2.4 Pain Relievers

The Pain Relievers section of a Value Proposition Canvas helps businesses identify the solutions they can offer to their customers in order to solve their pain points. Pain points are the problems or challenges that customers are facing in their day-to-day lives. Pain relievers provide solutions to those pain points so that customers can experience a better quality of life. These solutions could include products or services that help customers save time, save money, improve their health, increase their productivity, or provide them with convenience. Pain relievers should be specific, measurable, and achievable for the business to implement. Examples of pain relievers could include automated services, fast delivery, subscription options, discounts, or special offers.

- Define what is innovation.
- How to communicate with the market?
- How to use the law for innovation?
- With the right methods, tasks can take less time.
- Trainings can help people get started faster.
- Staff exchange helps break down barriers between municipalities, and develop empathy, as well as shared practices and understanding.
- Share experiences in the trainings and give the audience contacts for further questions about More knowledge.

3.2.5 Gain Creators

Gain creators are a particular type of value proposition. They are those specific benefits, features, and solutions that the customer will gain from the product or service. Gain creators should be tailored to the customer's specific needs and should be framed in terms of how they will deliver value to the customer. Examples of gain creators include improved convenience, increased efficiency, cost savings, enhanced safety, improved quality, and increased user satisfaction. By focusing on the customer's needs and delivering value through gain creators, businesses can create and communicate a compelling value proposition.

- Workshops are a good way of engaging and studying the market.
- Tackle specific problem.
- Workshops offer a chance for procurers to connect and use those connections also later.
- Business cases of good practices: to use the law for innovation.
- Workshop/meetings with the market.
- Opportunity to exchange even more with colleagues/other buyers.
- Examples of success stories
- Provide methodology how to record, import, and export best practice.

3.2.6 Statement

Combining all the insights generated from the empathy map and the value proposition canvas, the consortium used the Geoff Moore's format to generate the following general value proposition statement for procurers:

For Public Innovation Procurers who want to increase efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives – that provide deeper insights in a more accessible and understandable format than other alternatives.

3.3 Innovation Providers Value Proposition

The value proposition canvas is a framework which can help ensure that a product or service is positioned around what the customer values and needs. The value proposition canvas focuses on understanding the customers problems and producing products or services that solve them. Because telling people you have a great product does not make them want it. This chapter treats the innovation provider as the customer and elaborates on the brainstorming outputs leading to the value proposition statement.

3.3.1 Tasks

A company manager providing an innovative solution to public innovation procurers from a local municipality task would include:

- Understanding the needs, goals, objectives, and requirements of the local municipality.
- Conduct research.
- Interact with the stakeholders.
- Developing an innovative solution and make it in line with municipality demands.
- Presenting the solution to the public innovation procurers and communicate the benefits and value of the solution.
- Negotiating contracts and agreements
- Managing the project team, monitoring progress, and ensuring that the solution is delivered on time and within budget.

3.3.2 Pains

In carrying out the tasks, innovation providers encounter a multitude of challenges and difficulties. One of the most significant hurdles is the resource-intensiveness required to apply for calls with having only a small chance of success. This challenge is particularly pronounced for smaller companies that lack in-house knowledge and expertise regarding government dealings and relations. The complex nature of public procurement processes and regulations can make it difficult for companies to navigate these systems effectively, resulting in time-consuming and costly efforts that may not yield the desired outcomes. As such, innovation providers must be prepared to invest significant resources and effort into their application process while also upholding their day-to-day operations.

- Takes a lot of time and resources to apply for a small chance to win.

-
- Knowledge to have government relations is not within the company.
 - Government likes to deal with one big client rather than with many small ones.

3.3.3 Gains

The gains of providing existing solutions as innovations for the public sector is the opportunity to enter new markets with lower risks (after winning), and a long-term partnership. Additionally, having one a tender once increases your future potential to win other tenders and provide solutions to other municipalities.

3.3.4 Value

The tasks, activities, and deliverables of the BUILD consortium create value to innovation providers as they remove pains and expand on gains. They do so by building internal capacity to win tenders, allow them to voice concerns, and provide networking opportunities.

- Build internal capacity to win tenders.
- Voice concerns.
- Help procurers become better.

3.3.5 Statement

Combining all the insights generated from the discussions and the value proposition canvas, the consortium used the Geoff Moore's format to generate the following general value proposition statement for providers:

For Public Innovation Providers who want to increase their application efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives – that offer a direct personal connection to procurers.

4 Engagement strategy

4.1 Tailoring the tasks for the audience based on Value Proposition

When engaging stakeholders and recipients of the BUILD activities, it is important to tailor the messaging to highlight its unique value in a way that resonates the most with the receivers. In the case of the BUILD project, this is different for the innovation provider than it is for the procurer. This is why the table below directly relates the BUILD activities to the value proposition to create a unique message for each.

Provider <i>"For Public Innovation Providers who want to increase their application efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives - that offer a direct personal connection to procurers."</i>	Tasks	Procurer <i>"For Public Innovation Procurers who want to increase efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives - that provide deeper insights in a more accessible format than other alternatives."</i>
<p>"Learn who are the most important points of connections with the government in your local area!"</p> <p>"Mapping key ecosystem actors enables public innovation providers to better understand the needs and expectations of their stakeholders, leading to more user-centred and effective solutions."</p> <p>"Mapping key ecosystem actors is a crucial step towards building a strong network of partners who share a common goal of creating impactful and sustainable public solutions."</p> <p>"In the complex ecosystem of public innovation, mapping key actors is essential to understanding the interconnectedness of stakeholders and harnessing their collective power."</p>	<p>Mapping key actors (T3.2)</p>	<p>"Discover your own best practices and valuable networks!"</p> <p>"Learn about what other procurers are doing to become efficient in a comprehensive overview".</p> <p>"The power of mapping key ecosystem actors is not just in identifying the players, but in unlocking the potential of collaborative innovation that can transform public services."</p> <p>"By mapping key ecosystem actors, public innovation procurers gain a strategic advantage in accessing the expertise and resources they need to drive meaningful change."</p>
<p>"In the world of public innovation, networking meetings between providers and procurers are essential to forge strong partnerships and drive meaningful change."</p>	<p>Networking meetings (T2.2)</p>	<p>"By attending networking meetings with innovation providers, procurers gain unique insights into the latest innovations."</p> <p>"Meeting innovation providers face-to-face outside of a procurement process can be an opportunity to learn about barriers faced by</p>

"By attending networking meetings with public innovation procurers, providers gain unique **insights into the needs and expectations** of their stakeholders, leading to more effective and user-centered solutions."

"Gain the insights and skills you need to create **more effective, user-centered, and sustainable public solutions** and learn about how public innovation procurers operate."

"Knowledge pills will help you **expand and maintain your internal capacity** of participating in public procurement processes".

N/A

N/A

Knowledge Pills (T5.3)

Training sessions (T4.1, T4.3)

Staff exchanges (T4.2)

providers when applying, as it removes the immediate pressure. This can help your municipality **design more user-centered processes.**"

"Power-packed shots of insights and inspiration that can transform the way they approach their work."

"In the fast-paced world of public innovation, knowledge pills are essential to **staying up to date** on the latest trends, technologies, and best practices."

"Learn from the best to become **more efficient** in your innovation procurement processes. This will help your department save time, and avoid unnecessary risks, whilst conforming to European standards."

"Staff exchanges are essential to build networks, share best practices, and foster collaboration between different organizations and sectors."

4.2 Engagement Gantt Chart

5 Conclusion

Trough organising interactive workshops, a unique value proposition statement has been created for innovation procurers as well as providers that reflects the input from all partners. These statements play a crucial role in tailoring the messaging of the various BUILD activities and deliverables to ensure proper engagement according to the Gantt chart provided.

This report can be used as a guideline in all future BUILD deliverables.

6 Annex

6.1 Leaflet

BUILD Project

Boosting the demand for innovative goods and services in Europe by promoting the use of public procurement of sustainable innovation and increasing capacities of cities in innovation procurement.

HOW

- Encouraging cooperation and knowledge sharing between public buyers.
- Discovering the most up-to-date innovative technological solutions and assisting in their development.
- Linking and establishing synergies with research and innovation projects.

MISSION OF IMPACT

- Raising interest and awareness about the PPI.
- Dedicating training and guidance, exchange of best practices and capacity building.

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www.build-procurement.eu

6.2 Presentation

Value proposition statement and engagement strategy.

Lucas de Bont, CIVITTA

14.04.2023

The following logic was used to ensure that all partner input is used in the creation of the value proposition and engagement strategy:

Frameworks

- Partners went through all the steps of the **Empathy Map** and **Value proposition Canvas** for the public innovation procurers which resulted in newly found insights and a deeper understanding of the purpose of BUILD.
- An **empathy map** is a collaborative tool a team can use to gain a deeper insight into their customers.
- The **value proposition canvas** is a framework which can help ensure that a product or service is positioned around what the customer values and needs.
- Each step consisted of a five-minute **brainstorm**. Afterwards, post-it results were quickly clustered along overarching themes. All the input generated from the brainstorming exercise has been analyzed and will be presented in its raw form as well as in a short summary.

Value Proposition Statements

For **Public Innovation Procurers** who want to increase efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives – that provide deeper insights in a more accessible and understandable format than other alternatives.

For **Public Innovation Providers** who want to increase their application efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives – that offer a direct personal connection to procurers.

Tailoring the tasks for the audience based on Value Proposition

Provider	Tasks	Procurer
<p><i>"For Public Innovation Providers who want to increase their application efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives - that offer a direct personal connection to procurers."</i></p> <p>"Learn who are the most important points of connections with the government in your local area!"</p> <p>"Mapping key ecosystem actors enables public innovation providers to better understand the needs and expectations of their stakeholders, leading to more user-centred and effective solutions."</p> <p>"Mapping key ecosystem actors is a crucial step towards building a strong network of partners who share a common goal of creating impactful and sustainable public solutions."</p> <p>"In the complex ecosystem of public innovation, mapping key actors is essential to understanding the interconnectedness of stakeholders and harnessing their collective power."</p>	<p>Mapping key actors (T3.2)</p>	<p><i>"For Public Innovation Procurers who want to increase efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives - that provide deeper insights in a more accessible format than other alternatives."</i></p> <p>"Discover your own best practices and valuable networks!"</p> <p>"Learn about what other procurers are doing to become efficient in a comprehensive overview".</p> <p>"The power of mapping key ecosystem actors is not just in identifying the players, but in unlocking the potential of collaborative innovation that can transform public services."</p> <p>"By mapping key ecosystem actors, public innovation procurers gain a strategic advantage in accessing the expertise and resources they need to drive meaningful change."</p>

Tailoring the tasks for the audience based on Value Proposition

Provider	Tasks	Procurer
<p><i>"For Public Innovation Providers who want to increase their application efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives - that offer a direct personal connection to procurers."</i></p> <p>"In the world of public innovation, networking meetings between providers and procurers are essential to forge strong partnerships and drive meaningful change."</p> <p>"By attending networking meetings with public innovation procurers, providers gain unique insights into the needs and expectations of their stakeholders, leading to more effective and user-centred solutions."</p>	<p>Networking meetings (T2.2)</p>	<p><i>"For Public Innovation Procurers who want to increase efficiency and find new opportunities, our Activities and Deliverables are Capacity Building and Networking Initiatives - that provide deeper insights in a more accessible format than other alternatives."</i></p> <p>"By attending networking meetings with innovation providers, procurers gain unique insights into the latest innovations."</p> <p>"Meeting innovation providers face-to-face outside of a procurement process can be an opportunity to learn about barriers faced by providers when applying, as it removes the immediate pressure. This can help your municipality design more user-centred processes."</p>

Thank you